

(Re)Presenting the Royal Glass Plate Collection

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ABSTRACT

This article documents my visit to Celebrating the National Glass Plate Negatives Registered as a UNESCO's Memory of the World, held at the National Museum, Bangkok, from late May to 28 July 2018. The UNESCO-registered Royal Collection, comprising nearly 35,427 glass plate negatives and 50,000 prints spanning 1855 to 1935, was originally preserved across three royal libraries belonging to King Chulalongkorn, King Vajiravudh, and Prince Damrongrajnubhab. The exhibition presented approximately 150 archival-quality digital prints across eight gallery rooms arranged in chronological order, tracing Siam's social, cultural, and political transformation during the era of Western colonisation in Asia.

Approaching the exhibition from my position as a photo-historical process practitioner, I reflect on the curatorial decision to exhibit digital reproductions rather than original materials, situating this choice within the competing demands of heritage preservation and public accessibility. I further identify the absence of photographer credits and technical information in the exhibition labels as a significant gap in the photo-historical reading of the collection.

Drawing on Rosalind Morris's account of photographer John Thomson's negotiations at the court of King Rama IV, I consider the camera as a diplomatic instrument, and examine how the practice of image-making was transmitted across royal generations, accumulating into the collection's present scale. I close by locating this encounter within a broader inquiry into Southeast Asian photographic histories, with particular attention to the relative scarcity of comparable pre-1900s collections in Malaya beyond the commercial studios of G.R. Lambert & Co. and Kleingrothe, and call for greater effort toward gathering and indexing Malayan photographic heritage for future scholarly access.

KEYWORDS

Bangkok, Glass Plate, Heritage, Memory of the World, National Archive Bangkok, National Museum Bangkok, Photography, Photography Exhibition, Photography History, Royal Collection, Thailand, UNESCO

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Exhibition Location: National Museum Bangkok, Na Phra That Alley, Khwaeng Phra Borom Maha Ratchawang, Khet Phra Nakhon, Bangkok 10200, Thailand

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Note

I personally would like to thank Tuan Izmal Karim for reminding me to attend this exhibition, in which, I was pleased with the visit, and it had established into something to look forward into in greater development of photographic history within the Southeast Asian region.

Exhibition banner illustrated from the collection of the Royal children of Prince Mahidol Adulyadej of Songkhla, image taken post 1925.

Exhibition display of one of the rooms

I took a chance to get on the first flight out to have a day visit over to Bangkok just to reach one of notable exhibition in the busy city of Bangkok, the 'Celebrating the National Glass Plate Negatives Registered as a UNESCO's Memory of the World', which is held over at the National Museum (a small colonial designed facility, which used to run for minting coin). The exhibition had started in the late of May, will end this coming 28th July 2018.

Being a practitioner in the photo-historical processes, it is a must for me to head over there to see this exhibition personally.

Extract from the UNESCO's site on the collection:

"The Royal Collection holds almost 35,427 glass plate negatives and 50,000 prints, covering a long and continuous period from 1855-1935, which were previously preserved in 3 separate royal libraries of the original owners: King Chulalongkorn, King Vajiravudh, and Prince Damrongrajanubhab. The nominated Collection are historical evidence featuring social, cultural, political changes and foreign relations activities of Siam, and its relations with the world. The Collection depicts national and international important personalities, places, and events, from the age of western colonization in Asia which prompted Siam to examine its national identity and to reform its society..."

Left to right: 'Indra God' depicted in a play, middle; "Yuen Kruang", male actor for the same character; right: traditional dance for female actress, both refer to the play as how it was done in the fourth reign.

As I walked through the exhibition, mind you, I do prefer to see such ambitious collection to be in original silver based prints, or seeing the original negative plates, and the cameras involved. But, I understand leaving such precious materials on public display poses significant risks; from its heritage and economic value, to the risk of being in an environment that will damage the original materials; as the environment in Bangkok being hot and humid all the time.

Controlled environment would be ideal, but out of costs involved and to air-conditioned the entire property will damage the value of the site itself as well. The print outs from high-resolution scans would be sufficient to be displayed instead, works both ways in acknowledging the collection and the key point image, which I believe it was hard to decide among the tens of thousands of images involved!

Somdet Phra Buddhacarya (Brahmaramsi) Wat Rakhang Khositaram.

About 150 prints displayed, these were scanned from the plate negatives; that was observed to be printed roughly 3 to 5 feet from digital archival paper prints. Such size seems to be appropriate to the given space.

The exhibition was divided into 8 room segments that have a linear movement from the front towards the back of the gallery. From the inception of photographic survey on the community towards the presence of the Siam's as an Empire, the illustrated life of the Royal families, and finally ended with a note of the Royal families' interest in utilising photographic tools as a part of their life. On the first glance going through the exhibition, it seems to be of chronological order, depicting the phases what Siam goes through.

On another run through, it had also indicated the actions in making photography were present, the camera itself being acknowledged and utilised as a tool, a sort of an interlocutor; in

King Narai's Palace in Lopburi Province.

General Somdet Phra Chao Boromwongthoe Phra Ong Chao Rangsit Prayurasakdi. Image taken in the reign of King Vajiravudth, in royal decorated gown.

Carts and barges along the bank of Nan river.

Sakai Boy from Phatalung, adopted as courtier in the Grand Palace by King Chulalongkorn. Dressed in character of 'Khanang', a private in the folk play ("Wild Tiger Corps" and Royal Thai Traditional Band). The young boy plays as Chao Ngo character in Sang Thong; also in part of the King Chulalongkorn's inspiration in his written play, "Ngo Paa".

order to acknowledge the established monarchs and the important figures. It moves towards a form of social survey, which was mostly missing in the exhibited prints. This, I might assume, had remained in the rest of undisplayed plates.

The entire exhibition were focused on the celebration in the position of the monarch and their family. Which would be the case as the images were straight forward, direct, and asserting authority. Though it imposes their stature the position held over their subjects, yet, there are images which cuts into segments where we start seeing the royal family possesses more humble, and content family life.

It was considered that the King Rama IV (King Mongkut of Siam) is sacred, in which lesser subject aren't allowed to look directly towards the King himself live in person. I recall reading Rosalind Morris' explanation, in which the renowned photographer, John Thomson, managed to convince the King to have the exact image of his likeness made. Paraphrasing Morris, various photographic tools were given as diplomatic gifts for the King, in which had certainly piqued His Highness' curiosity in the image usage however it could to benefit the country, and establishing greater acknowledgement of His and the royal families presence to the world.

King Mongkut: Taken in 1867 when preaching the Dhamma Sermon to the Inner Court Department on Visakha Puja Day. In religious attire, red loin cloth with breast cloth cover.

King Chulalongkorn's subjects celebrated His return from Europe on November 17th, 1907 at Paknam, Samut Prakan Province.

Royal children of Prince Mahidol Adulyadej of Songkhla, image taken post 1925.

Court Girl of the Princess Consort, Princess
Saisavak, Bhironvya Krom Phra Suddhasimant,
Prince Krom Krom Vorachakra Dharamonart, son of King Rama II. Image of a daguerreotype, estimated to
have been taken during the third reign (prior 1851)

This excites me of what I had seen images of the South East Asian photo-histories so far was limited to the books I have in my own personal library. Never had I realised before of a collection exists in this magnitude, or in this case, the digital prints seems to be the representation of the kept treasures.

Siamese Nobleman, taken during the reign of King Rama IV.

Prince Mahamala Krom Phraya Bamrap
Parapaksa (Somdet Chao Fa Klang)

It would be just that my own preference perhaps, to see the actual photographic historical objects in the exhibition, rather than the modern representation, or modern medium (digital prints) made of from it.

It could be arguable the value of objects, or image-objects in this case, should not be measured qualitatively the same value of the subject it illustrated. Simply saying, the original objects are of equal interest just as much as the image arrived from it.

However, as I mentioned before, the risks in releasing the highly valued materials in the opened environment would be devastating if damage, loss, or deterioration happens upon them. Hence, I understood the decision in having the exhibitions in a form of printed copies of it. Much like how the Mona Lisa exhibited at the Louvre might be a copy? But lets not go there on that particular example.

Prince Damrongrajanubhab's children, Left to right: M.C. Saphasombun, M.C. Pathanayu, M.C. Phailailekha, M.C. Siwaliwilat, and M.C. Disanuwat Diskul. Image taken at the Pratu Samyod Palace.

To see this exhibition, had gave the needed motivation for me to realise that histories were etched much more vividly as photographic histories as well, in which had different approach to look at, as these were seen more than just visual supplements for any historical texts.

King Chulalongkorn posing together with His children. Taken at the Bang Pa-In Palace.

Such represented images tells greater amount of visual narratives, besides the obvious part that it is about Siam, I began to see the intention of the photographers, the instructions given for them to pose, the little minute details, the attempt in re-creating spaces that implies beyond the studio settings (backdrops that was painted of the outdoor sceneries, exotic locations and places).

The sitter's postures and gaze, the objects surrounds them, even the usual excitement in seeing another

Royal members of the Inner court with their cameras. Left to right: Princess Nibha Nobhadol, Princess Malini Nobhadara, Chao Chom Uen, Chao Chom Erb, and Princess Oraprabandh Rambai.

Chao Chom Erb preparing to take portrait of Chao Phraya Surabandh.

Chao Phraya Surabandh, taken by Chao Chom Erb.

Winner of the Siam Motorcycle Racing on October 30, 1920, Khun Sanphakit Vijarna. Image was taken for commercial advertisement.

A closer look will find interesting details in re-touching attempt to cover an ideal look, as the rider and the Harley Davidson bike to appear to be 'in transit'.

image within the photographs, scrutinising, and to recognise them as best representative of themselves within social order.

Photo-historians reads all these sorts of information, and utilise it as the main form of context into reading into the moment when the image was made. In most cases, these images were done in a way that the sitters wanted made to be the best representation of themselves.

I do prefer to see the actual materials; the negatives, the tools, remnants of the photo-chemistries... etc., as it is just as important to know the making of it and to understand towards its making.

Most likely this desire comes as an interest as I am a practitioner of this craft myself. The act in deciphering the actions through the tools of their use seems to be just as important as the final image itself. It is still a quirk that I enjoyed doing.

King Rama VII, overseeing the move of King Rama VI book collections to a new library, “Vajiravudh Library”

Image taken of elderly women during an inspection by Prince Damrongrajnubhab's tour in Monthon Udon, 1906.

Context are important, however, I always see most of the information missing; who were the photographers, the person behind the camera, the medium utilised, and so forth, to be missing. These are the potholes into reading the material further.

It felt the images then receded into the background, and become supplement to the narratives given. Almost unjustifiably use, which the image in turn becomes much like a decoration. I strongly believe, this would be a greater aspiration to explore further.

There are numerous writings that will explain well in the history of Siam through photography, however, what excites me was the existence of significant collection exists on the home ground itself. The usual arrangements were usually any sort of important collection had always been in another museum in far away in the West, usually almost exclusive in closed collection.

What contributed towards the impressive amount of collection would be the practice of photography had piqued the interest of King Rama IV himself. The joy in image-making were shared among the Royal family, the helpers, and those who are close to him. The practice was inherited to his children and so on, which they themselves are just as passionate and image-makers in their own rights. Such collective and inherited efforts, had accumulated and projected into massive collection, which deserved the award to be part of the world's memory.

It would be true that photography is an expensive craft as it relies on the use of silver. The photographic apparatus were imported goods, and the time spent in making them certainly of those who are able to afford it. Such practice were in tune for those with wealth, and of those in power, access to the vernacular and sights of the daily norms; which now became be highly treasured information. In which differs from the Western counterparts, whereby early photographic processes could be practiced by most that could afford it.

I could see that more narratives will arrive to the study of this collection, considering that various marks in mankind's history had gone through numerous maladies of war and certainly misplaced, damaged, and disjointed photographic histories. I see this as a motivation, inspiration, and the drive to look into Malaya's own photographic histories.

Court Girl of the Princess Consort, Princess
Saisavali Bhiromya Krom Phra Suddhasininat

Though, what Malaya/Malaysia have would be of the late Almarhum Sultan Ismail Nasiruddin Shah of Terengganu, in which he is a fantastic photographer of the time, yet there isn't yet other before him that managed a massive collective works done in the past prior 1900s with an exception from the G.R. Lambert & Co. Studio, Kleingrothe, etc. (I do sincerely hope there would be one great massive collection of Malaya gathered and indexed that will be accessible for future research).

Please note these photographs are taken during the exhibition period and shared here for reference. I highly encourage to the readers to visit the exhibition in this limited time, hopefully that this will be repeating events with more detailed or another look into other plates. You could also purchase a copy of their catalogue, which is also an impressive volume, and plate counts in the book were even more than what was exhibited. The book could be purchased from the National Archive in Bangkok after the exhibition period, as per conversation I had with their staff over at the exhibition gallery.

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